

A proposed input to the ecotourism development plan of Balite falls in Amadeo, Cavite

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Abstract

The Philippines is gifted with wondrous marine biodiversity and natural sceneries. It was in 1999 when an executive order was passed to preserve and conserve the natural resources of the country. As there are various ways and strategies on how to guard our natural resources, one of those is to create a tourism development plan. This study aims to protect and conserve Balite Falls in Amadeo Cavite by providing insights into its ecotourism development plan. Specifically, it illustrates the relationship between the level of perception of respondents about Balite Falls and the respondents' demographic profile. Applied research method was used in this study. The data collected was from a mix of locals from Amadeo and tourists from Balite Falls who were studied and surveyed. Results showed that there is no significant relationship between the two variables, which then became the foundation of the researchers' insights into the input of the ecotourism development plan of Balite Falls.

Keywords: Balite Falls; Ecotourism development plan; Ecotourism; Amadeo.

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Introduction

The International Ecotourism Society (TIES) defined ecotourism as a responsible travel to natural areas while conserving the environment and nurturing the wellness of the locals (Bricker, 2017). Center for Responsible Travel (CREST) thoroughly explained that ecotourism is efficient traveling to untouched areas that conserves the environment socially and economically and preserving the well-being of local people whilst generating knowledge and understanding of the destination and the locals (CREST, 2017). Ecotourism aims to improve tourist accommodations, attractions, local flora and fauna, local people, and the travel industry.

Ecotourism provides quality tourist products, investments, job opportunities, and development of the place. Ecotourism intends to support the conservation of the environment and wildlife. Taking advantage of these natural resources means wrecking natural landscapes and damaging the habitats of wildlife. There is a need to maintain natural resources, as it can save the lives of the animals and their habitat. Locals depend on natural resources – it is where they acquire their source of living. Ecotourism can support the livelihood of the communities. Ecotourism provides healing, relaxation, and excitement to the tourist. Keeping ecotourism also means to preserve and experience the diverse cultures of various communities. It can open people's minds to different cultures and views around the world. Knowing the history of the tourism destination is also a benefit of ecotourism tourists can have.

In the Philippines, the local government also provided an ecotourism plan such as the Oriental Mindoro Strategic Action Plan for marine protected areas, as well as in Bohol to conserve tarsier and other animal species, and the Chocolate Hills. The Philippines is gifted with natural resources that is why it is the Pearl of the Orient Seas. Ecotourism in the Philippines was recognized in 1991 when various organizations worked with the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and the World Trade Organization (WTO). It was only formally introduced during the second National Tourism Congress (NTC) in 1992 (Abat-Parducho, 2016). To establish the framework of ecotourism in the Philippines, Executive Order 111 was passed in 1999. Wherein, the nation shall vouch to protect and conserve the country's cultural heritage and natural resources for the present and future generations to benefit from it.

Over the years, the Philippines has encountered problems and challenges. Currently, one of the major problems is solid waste mismanagement. Solid wastes keep on increasing due to the increment of population. In 2016, solid wastes in the country have a total of 40,087.45 tons (Senate Economic Planning Office, 2017). Solid waste is a threat to the health and safety of the people and the environment. These solid wastes can contaminate bodies of water. It takes up to 1,000 years for plastic bags to degrade.

Philippines is also experiencing degradation of natural resources and biodiversity. Illegal logging has caused millions of old forests to deteriorate. Because of deforestation, there is no place for water storage, thus, flooding occurs. That is why a tourism development is needed.

Tourism development is defined as a sustainable improvement of a tourism destination; it retains and balances the number of tourist rates. The goal of a tourism development plan is to help a certain destination to enhance its captivating quality and by that, it can attract more tourists; it provides benefits for both tourists and the locals. Tourism can help the locals through the economic benefit of the area by providing recreational activities and improving infrastructures. The tourism development plan helps increase job rates and make revenue. It preserves the natural and cultural heritage of a destination. Thus, this research intends to propose insights by presenting an input to the ecotourism development plan.

Background of the Study

Amadeo is a municipality under the province of Cavite. It is situated in the southern part of the province. The town is surrounded by General Trias at the North, Silang at the East, Indang at the West, and Tagaytay in the South. Amadeo holds its pride for being the Coffee Capital of the Philippines. Pahimis Festival is created to celebrate its bounty coffee production. Amadeo also takes pride in its untouched nature. Its water forms: such as rivers, springs, and underground water are located at barangay Poblacion and other rural barangays as well. The well-known water forms are Balite Falls, Cañas River, Banga River, and Bolboc Spring. The residents also get its supply of potable water from the different forms of water.

Balite Falls is located in Barangay Poblacion. It is a perfect escape from the busy city, as it is very peaceful. The study was made to conserve Balite Falls and to prevent it from further damages made by humans. It also plans to raise awareness and educate people that they have a responsibility to protect natural tourist attractions like Balite Falls.

Ecotourism Development Plan

According to Kim et al. (2017), tourists visit an attraction due to its cultural sustainability. Traveling has become convenient in this modern age. As there are a lot of ways how to arrange a hotel accommodation, book a travel ticket, and arrange your preferred tour. Traveling created a bridge toward the different types of tourism. These types of tourism are slowly catching the public's attention and business stakeholders. One type of tourism is Ecotourism. According to Wishitemi et al. (2015), ecotourism makes a path for the global economy; thus, it can be seen as one of the many ways natural resources can be used sustainably while reducing the poverty of the area.

According to Silva (2015) ecotourism is not only focused on promoting and conserving biodiversity and natural resources, but it also focuses on the historical, socio-cultural, political, and economics of the community. Das and Chatterjee (2015) also added that the main objective of ecotourism is to help the locals engage and make a livelihood. Cobbinah (2015) also joined the debate by adding that promoting cultural preservation, environmental education and conservation are one of the most famous ecotourism principles.

All things can deteriorate if not handled properly, especially natural resources. Not everyone who visits a tourist destination are considerate and careful enough to protect and conserve the natural resources. Boracay is a great example; it was closed for six months due to tourist congestion and illegal waste disposal of business establishments and both locals and tourists. This temporary closure helped influence tourists to visit other Philippine tourist attractions. However, for an ecotourism to be used for a very long time, conservation of natural resources and maintenance of biodiversity is a must (Wishitemi et al., 2015). Various private and public organizations together with the help of business owners and government are taking steps to help protect and conserve natural resources. These steps are not produced overnight – they are a product of months of preparation and continuous study to know the possible negative and positive effects that might occur.

Locals and residents are also affected in a tourism development plan. Residents living beside the chosen tourism destination can be affected if the tourism development plan requires to have a bigger space. Abiodun and Oladeji (2018) states that rural and urban planning is the solution to eliminate residential crisis and to avoid the residents to move out. Ketema (2015) also included that the residents should not be excluded in monitoring the tourism destination. Chandel and Mishra (2016) also indicated that respect toward the local and indigenous culture should be practiced.

Employees should be equipped with good manners and etiquette, as these will help the tourist destinations attract potential business partners and tourists. Making tourists feel secure will also help in meeting the satisfaction (Chandel & Mishra, 2016). Chandel and Mishra (2016) also included that for tourists to fully appreciate the tourism area, they must directly and personally experience the area. Tourists also appreciate if they are given a personal time and when needed help, assistance will only be provided.

It is much appreciated if different stakeholders will generously contribute for the conservation of nature (Chandel & Mishra, 2016). These stakeholders include the local government unit, private and public organizations, and business owners and corporation. According to Chandel and Mishra (2016) the different activities of the stakeholders should benefit the locals economically.

Ketema (2015) heavily implies that establishing rules and regulations for the site should also be the top priority. Ecotourism policies should be formulated on striving to educate and provide understanding while inviting tourists, since conservation of natural resources is a top priority (Rhama, 2018). According to Wishitemi et al. (2015), businesses investing and are planning to invest in ecotourism should consider different factors such as conserving the natural resources and preserving the cultural heritage of the site.

Aswita (2018) heavily implies that the tourism development plan should educate and teach the public on how to sustain the natural environment. Ecotourism and environmental education are two concepts and ideas that should not be separated and should support each other. Having a strong education background about the environment influences the tourists and the locals, and even the private and public organizations to practice environmental conservation.

According to Jemal (2016), natural resources can be preserved and developed by providing the right ecotourism plan. The implementation of a well-thought ecotourism development plan can help increase awareness in conserving and preserving the tourism site. It can also help to encourage the locals and tourists to be responsible (Cahyadi et al., 2019). If the tourism destination resource is handled properly, it will make a big impact on the economy and will help the local's livelihood (Bhuiyan et al., 2015). Hunt et. al. (2015) stated that ecotourism provides employment to support the locals. Kazeminia et al. (2016) stated that if the tourists show high amount of interest due to the newly developed ecotourism site, they are willing to pay any amount. As a result, these newly developed ecotourism sites will help the community and the municipality to be their source of income (Hameed & Khalid, 2018). Overall, if the tourism development plan is properly thought of, it will make an impact to various factors.

Statement of the Problem

This research aims to protect and conserve Balite Falls by presenting a proposed input to the ecotourism development plan. This input will help make insights for an ecotourism development plan of Balite Falls. It hopes to answer the following:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Gender
 - 1.3. Occupation
 - 1.4. Income
 - 1.5. Number of visits made to the falls
2. What is the level of perception of the respondents toward their views about the Balite Falls, in terms of the following factors?
 - 2.1. Accessibility
 - 2.2. On its beauty
 - 2.3. On helping the government
 - 2.4. As a tourist attraction
 - 2.5. Cleanliness and maintenance
 - 2.6. Facilities
 - 2.7. Transportation
 - 2.8. Management
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of perception of the respondents about Balite Falls and the demographic profile?
4. Based on the results of the study, what action plan can be made as an input to the ecotourism development plan of Balite Falls?

Methodology

Research Design

Correlational research is a design that measures two variables to calculate and evaluate the statistical relationship between the variables. The design used in this study answered the question on the significant relationship between the level of perception in Balite Falls and the demographic profile of the respondents.

Sample

The researchers randomly picked 50 locals in Amadeo and 50 tourists in Balite Falls; there were 100 respondents for the study. The researchers had come up with the idea of surveying the whole site, to get the data that will allow them to strengthen the project's importance. With that, the researchers decided to use simple random sampling and randomly pick one hundred respondents (100) - a combination of locals in Amadeo and tourists in Balite Falls.

Instruments

To obtain the data needed for the study, the researchers formulated questionnaires that were used to gather the information and data needed. The conduct of the research involves the use of questionnaires which were used as a survey form, with that the respondents were guided by the researchers towards the research objectives. The questionnaires were divided into three parts – profile of the respondents, a ranking scale where researchers used a Likert scale to collect the perception of the respondents on the different factors regarding Balite Falls, and the last part where respondents were asked if they have any suggestions regarding Balite Falls.

The first part of the questionnaire was the profile of respondents; it was composed of age, gender, occupation, income, and number of visits made to the falls. On the second part of the questionnaire, researchers used a five-point Likert Scale to thoroughly collect the level of perception of the respondents. The Likert Scale was composed of five points; 1 – Strongly Disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 – Agree, and 5 – Strongly Agree.

Data Collection

The researchers used questionnaires in gathering all the data needed. The researchers asked the permission of Amadeo's Head of Tourism Department to conduct a survey.

Data Analysis Procedure

The following statistical tools were used to analyze the data:

1. **Frequency – Average.** To calculate the data of the profile of the respondents, the frequency – percentage was used. The profile of the respondents was composed of age, gender, occupation, income, and number of visits made to the falls.
2. **Pearson-R Correlation.** To determine the relationship of the level of perception in Balite Falls and the demographic profile of the respondents.

Results

Respondents' Profile

Table 1. Distribution of the profile of the respondents according to age (n=100)

Age Group	F	%
18-25	51	51%
26-32	17	17%
33-39	12	12%
40-47	8	8%
48-53	12	12%

Out of 100 respondents, it could be seen that 51% are from the age group 18-25. This can be interpreted that most of the visitors of Balite Falls are from the ages of 18 to 25 years old. The second age group is 26-32 years old with 17%. While the ages 40-47 has the least population with 8%.

Table 2. Distribution of the profile of the respondents according to gender (n=100)

Gender	F	%
Male	43	43%
Female	55	55%
Not Indicated	2	2%

The table shows the percentage of respondents who visited Balite Falls according to gender. Out of 100 respondents, 55% are females and 43% are males while the remaining 2% did not indicate their gender. The result shows that more than half of the respondents who visited Balite Falls are females.

Table 3. Distribution of the profile of the respondents according to occupation (n=100)

Occupation	F	%
Student	21	21%
Sales Officer	1	1%
Crime Registrar	1	1%
Tricycle Driver	1	1%
Driver	4	4%
Cashier	1	1%
Maid	1	1%
Security Guard	1	1%
Factory Worker	1	1%
Government Employee	3	3%
General Manager	1	1%
Operations Manager	1	1%
Watch Man	3	3%
Policewoman	1	1%
Police Officer	2	2%
Nursing Assistant	1	1%
Tour Guide	1	1%
Kagawad	1	1%
Lifeguard	1	1%
Clerk – PIO	1	1%
Not Indicated	52	52%

The table shows the distribution of respondents according to profession. 52% of the respondents did not indicate their profession, 21% are students and the remaining percentage are divided into individuals who are working in different industries. This shows that Balite Falls is visited by both professionals and non-professionals. This also shows that majority of the respondents came from various occupations that has no relation with visiting Balite Falls.

Table 4. Distribution of the profile of the respondents according to income (n=100)

Income	F	%
P10000-20000	51	51%
P20000-30000	16	16%
P30000-40000	3	3%
P40000-50000	4	4%
P50000 and up	2	2%
Not Working	22	22%
Not Stated	2	2%

This is the distribution of the respondents' profile according to income. According to the statistics stated in Table 4, there is a total of 51% who has an income of Php 10,000 – 20,000 per month; 16% has an income of Php 20,000 – 30,000; 4% has an income of Php 40,000 – 50,000; 3% has an income of Php 30,000 – 40,000; and 2% has an income of Php 50,000 and higher.

Table 5. Distribution of the profile of the respondents according to number of visits made to the falls (n=100)

Visits Made to the Falls	F	%
1-3	66	66%
4-6	17	17%
7-9	8	8%
10-12	0	0%
13 and up	9	9%

The table shows the number of times the respondents were able to visit Balite Falls. Majority of them visited the tourist attraction one (1) to three (3) times with 66%. 17% of the respondents have visited the place for four (4) to six (6) times, 8% for seven (7) to nine (9) times, and 9% for more than 13 times. This can be interpreted that they enjoy visiting the falls.

Perception of the Respondents

Table 6. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls' accessibility

Accessibility	Average	Verbal Interpretation
The Falls can easily be reached by visitors.	3.76	Agree
The Falls has a social media that people can search.	3.98	Agree
The Falls has a website that people can look up to.	3.80	Agree
The Falls has a contact number that people can easily contact.	3.88	Agree
The Falls can be visited by neighboring cities and provinces easily.	4.11	Agree
The Falls has an email address where they can send inquiries.	3.70	Agree
Total	3.87	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 6 illustrates the average scores of the respondents' description about the accessibility of Balite Falls. The highest statement under accessibility is *"The neighboring cities can visit Balite Falls easily"* which has 4.11. The lowest criteria are *"The Falls can be easily reached by visitors"*, with a computed data of 3.76.

Table 7. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls regarding on its beauty

On its Beauty	Average	Verbal Interpretation
Balite Falls is a hidden gem of Amadeo.	4.28	Strongly Agree
Balite Falls has a picturesque view.	4.30	Strongly Agree
Balite Falls is Instagram-worthy.	4.05	Strongly Agree
Balite Falls has a relaxing vibe.	4.31	Strongly Agree
Balite Falls has a magnificent scene as a waterfall.	4.22	Strongly Agree
Balite Falls is covered with trees and plants.	4.43	Strongly Agree
Total	4.27	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 7 indicates the respondents' description of Balite Falls according to its beauty. For this category, the respondents gave a very high rating on describing the beauty of Balite Falls. It got a total of 4.27 with a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree." This implies that Balite Falls has attracted tourists with its picturesque beauty. "Balite Falls is covered with plants" was the statement that got the highest rating with 4.43 and has a verbal interpretation of "strongly agree."

Table 8. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls on helping the government

On Helping the Government	Average	Verbal Interpretation
Balite Falls provides job employment.	3.99	Agree
Balite Falls creates opportunities for small medium enterprises.	3.70	Agree
Balite Falls has helped the government by increasing the tourist arrival.	3.98	Agree
Balite Falls is an income generator of the government.	3.82	Agree
Balite Falls is a tourism product of Amadeo.	4.21	Strongly Agree
Balite Falls helps promote Amadeo.	4.28	Strongly Agree
Total	4.00	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 8 illustrates the average score of the respondents' description on how Balite Falls helps the government. The highest statement was 4.28 with a verbal interpretation that falls on the category of "strongly agree." It can be implied that aside from the coffee of Amadeo, Balite Falls has helped Amadeo in promoting the municipality.

Table 9 illustrates the respondents' description of Balite Falls as a tourist attraction. Findings revealed that the criteria *"Balite Falls is perfect for healing and relaxation"* got the highest ranking with 4.31 or "strongly agree".

This statement can be interpreted that Balite falls exudes a serene vibe that might be one of the reasons why tourists like to go to this waterfall. The total average of Table 9 is 4.06; that falls under the verbal interpretation of agree.

Table 9. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls as a tourist attraction

Tourist Attraction	Average	Verbal Interpretation
Balite Falls is a famous tourist attraction in Amadeo.	4.13	Agree
Balite Falls is perfect for healing and relaxation.	4.31	Strongly Agree
Balite Falls is a kid-friendly tourist attraction.	3.97	Agree
Balite Falls is perfect for quick weekend getaway.	4.05	Agree
Balite Falls is perfect for summer vacation.	4.19	Agree
Balite Falls is a senior-friendly tourist attraction.	3.72	Agree
Total	4.06	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 10. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls' performance according on its cleanliness and maintenance

Cleanliness and Maintenance	Average	Verbal Interpretation
Trash are in the proper disposal.	4.01	Agree
The waste management is very effective.	4.03	Agree
The site has a frequent cleaner.	4.14	Agree
Public restrooms are well-maintained.	3.89	Agree
Foods that are sold on the site are clean and safe.	4.10	Agree
The staffs are well-groomed.	4.10	Agree
Total	4.05	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 10 shows the respondents perception of the cleanliness and maintenance of Balite Falls. Results showed that the site having a frequent cleaner got the highest score of 4.14. The lowest score was 3.89 under the statement *Public restrooms are well-maintained*, though still got a verbal interpretation of agree.

Aside from cleanliness and maintenance, facilities were also rated by the respondents. Results from Table 11 show a total average of 3.96 which can be interpreted that respondents rated Balite Falls' facilities positively. When calculating all the statements, facilities got a total average of 3.96 that can be interpreted verbally at "agree." The criteria *"There is an adequate supply of tables and chairs"* got the highest rating with 4.05 or agree. This statement can be interpreted that Balite Falls can accommodate a number of tourists.

Table 11. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls' performance according on its facilities

Facilities	Average	Verbal Interpretation
There is an adequate supply of table and chairs.	4.05	Agree
There are enough public restrooms.	3.96	Agree
Signages are easily seen by the tourists.	3.96	Agree
Selling and distribution of food is well-organized.	3.92	Agree
Foods that are sold on the site are inexpensive.	3.93	Agree
Security is highly implemented and prioritized.	3.96	Agree
Total	3.96	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 12. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls' performance according on its transportation

Transportation	Average	Verbal Interpretation
Transportation fees are cheap.	3.34	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Leaving the site is very easy, as there is enough transportation available.	3.29	Neither Agree nor Disagree
There are enough public buses when entering the site.	2.98	Neither Agree nor Disagree
There are enough public jeepneys when entering the site.	3.32	Neither Agree nor Disagree
There are enough tricycles when entering the site.	3.38	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Motorcycles and bicycles can enter the site safely.	4.00	Agree
Total	3.39	Neither Agree nor Disagree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

Table 12 indicates the perception of the respondents based on the transportation of Balite Falls. The category of transportation got a total of 3.39 with a verbal interpretation of "neither agree nor disagree." When entering the site, motorcycles and bicycles can freely enter the site. This statement got the highest rating of 4.00 with a verbal interpretation of agree.

Table 13. Average score of the respondents' description about Balite Falls' performance according on its management

Management	Average	Verbal Interpretation
Management and staff are friendly.	4.11	Agree
Management and staff are quick to fix minor problems.	4.01	Agree
There is an adequate amount of management and staff to accommodate the tourists.	4.06	Agree
Management and staff are well-educated about Balite Falls.	4.14	Agree
Management and staff are approachable.	4.22	Agree
Staffs are ready to assist the tourist.	4.26	Agree
Total	4.13	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.80 - Strongly Disagree; 1.81-2.60 - Disagree; 2.61-3.40 - Neither Agree nor Disagree; 3.41-4.20 - Agree; 4.21-5.00 - Strongly Agree

The table shows the respondents' description of the management of Balite Falls. The respondents see Balite Falls positively with a rating of 4.13 or "agree." The area that garnered the highest rank was "Staff are ready to assist the tourist" with 4.26, followed by "Management and staff are approachable" with 4.22.

Relationship of Level of Perception of the Respondents in Balite Falls and the Demographic Profile

Table 14. Relationship of the level of the respondents in Balite Falls to the demographic profile

Level of Perception vs Demographic Profile	Computed Pearson-R	Verbal Interpretation
Age	0.102	Small Positive
Gender	0.123	Small Positive
Occupation	-0.168	Weak Negative
Income	0.012	Small Positive
Number of Visits	0.045	Small Positive

In Table 14, Pearson-r was used to determine the significance of the level of perception of the respondents about Balite Falls and their demographic profile. The computed Pearson-r for the relationship of the level of perception of the respondents and the demographic profile age is 0.102. This can be interpreted that there is a small chance that age can interfere their decision to visit Balite Falls, especially people who are elderly. Still, Balite Falls is available for all ages.

The computed Pearson-r for the relationship of the level of perception of the respondents and demographic profile gender is 0.123. It has a verbal interpretation of small positive. This means that there is a low relationship with the level of perception and gender. This also means that there is a specific group based on gender that loves to visit the falls. Nonetheless, Balite Falls is not open to a specific gender only; it is open to all.

The computed correlation between the level of the perception of the respondents and their occupation is -0.168, with a verbal interpretation of weak negative, which can be interpreted that occupation is not a hindrance when visiting Balite Falls. 0.012 is the computed correlation between the relationship of the demographic profile income and the level of perception of the respondents. It also has a verbal interpretation of small positive, which means that they might consider their budget before visiting the falls. Nonetheless, the falls is affordable, that even students can experience the tourist attraction.

0.045 is the computed correlation between the relationship of the demographic profile number of visits and the level of perception of the respondents, with a verbal interpretation of small positive. This means that the number of visits the respondents made somehow affect their perception of the tourist attraction.

To sum it up, it shows that the demographic profile age, gender, occupation, income, and the number of visits made to the falls has no significant relationship with their level of perception of Balite Falls. However, as they continue to visit the falls for leisure and a quick escape from stressful school and work, there are some areas that Balite Falls should improve on. Nonetheless, the respondents will continue to visit the famous tourist attraction.

Input to the Ecotourism Development Plan of Balite Falls

The researchers summarized the input into three focal points: (1) expanding the market of Balite Falls through social media, transportation, and tourist products; (2) maintaining the beauty of the waterfalls, and (3) improving the visitors' satisfaction. These focal points covered the criteria that were included in the survey and statement of the problem. Those criteria are accessibility, on its beauty, as a tourist attraction, on helping the government, cleanliness and maintenance, transportation, facilities, and management; it was divided into three focal points to help future tourism plan makers to easily make guidelines, rules, plans, and resolutions.

The first focal point is to expand the market of Balite Falls using social media, transportation, and selling of tourist products. Advertising and marketing can open doors for markets both locally and internationally. It can boost the economy of the country and provide livelihood for the locals; expanding the market of Balite Falls, engaging social media influencers, and improving contact points can help (Haldrup, 2017; Nau, 2019; Tayao-Juego, 2020). Having a specialized point-to-point vehicle and producing #TatakBalite merch can be also considered.

The second focal point is to maintain and conserve the beauty of Balite Falls. The visual appearance plays a big role in tourist destination and attraction - it is the first thing that the tourists see. Tourists create their perception of the tourist destination based on the visual appearance. Balite Falls is surrounded with trees and plants, which makes it a great escape place from the concrete jungles. To maintain the appearance of the tourist attraction, there is a need to control the waste intake and to set a tourist carrying capacity.

The last point is to improve the tourists' satisfaction and their experience. Tourist satisfaction is very important to every tourist attraction as this can make or break the attraction. A tourist satisfaction is the feeling that the tourist has relative to his/her experience in a tourist attraction. To improve their satisfaction, their experience should be improved as well.

The researchers intend to help protect and conserve Balite Falls. Protect is a short-term effect while conserve is a long-term process. The researchers used this concept to make the action plan for the tourist attraction. Below is the framework that the researchers used on making the action plan. The results of the survey were the basis of the framework.

Figure 1. Action plan framework

The framework is shaped like a pyramid, which then is divided into two parts – to protect and to conserve.

I. PROTECT

A. Tourist Carrying Capacity

According to World Tourism Organization, tourism carrying capacity refers to the maximum number of people that a tourist destination can accommodate without causing physical, economic, socio-cultural, and environmental disturbance. The importance of a carrying capacity is that it measures the environmental sustainability. Carrying capacity protects the tourist attraction from damages due to overpopulation of tourists.

By setting a tourist carrying capacity, it can control the number of visitors per day. Aside from setting a tourist carrying capacity, personal data of the tourists such as name, age, address, and contact details should be obtained – this is to easily trace visitors when unexpected problems arise. The gathered date from the tourists must be 100% confidential.

1. **Improve Contact Platforms.** We are in a digital age, so it is very likely to have an active contact platform. The social media platform should be active, so the recurrent and future tourists can know what is new at the tourist attraction. The tourist attraction should establish a connection with the tourist not just physically, but also digitally. Creating contact platforms allows potential tourists to gain information and updates. It also helps the management to collect tourists' data, such as recommendations, insights, and their experiences. With this, it helps to improve protected areas just like Balite Falls. When tourists book a reservation through the platform, this can help the management control the number of tourists who will visit. This will also help them to trace the tourists' whereabouts whenever something unfortunate happens. With this, it will help protect the tourist attraction from overcrowding and potential imminent pollution.
2. **Specialized Vehicle Terminal.** The researchers have come up with the idea of having a specific van or tricycle terminal for tourists who use public transport when travelling. Travelling must not be complicated, rather, it should be tourist friendly. Tourists can use a single mode of transportation without compromising its safety, comfort, and budget. The local government can collaborate with the management of the Balite Falls to form a group of drivers who will pick up and drop off tourists. The terminal should be located at a place where there are many commuters. The staff will contact the personnel assigned on the terminal to pick up tourists who will go home. This idea will help visitors to easily access Balite falls. The falls is located near the highway although it is quite difficult to access public transport. With this idea, it can help locals be employed. This will also help in controlling the carrying capacity of the tourist attraction as people who made reservations through the contact platforms are the only people allowed to use the service.

B. Relation of Point-to-Point Vehicle and Creating Platforms to Tourist Carrying Capacity

Point-to-Point Vehicles and Contact Platforms work hand-in-hand. The tourist first inquires through any of the contact platforms in advance then the tourist will provide its personal details and his/her desired date. Next, the person-in-charge will arrange a vehicle for the tourist. With this, it will limit the number of tourists visiting the falls, thus preventing it from being overused.

C. Maintaining a Clean Environment

1. **Reduce, reuse, recycle.** Waste has always been difficult to dispose; the best thing that can we do is to create a waste management system in order to control waste and make Balite Falls safe and clean. It is inevitable to dispose plastic, but it can be managed. Placing trash bins at different areas of Balite Falls can prevent tourists from leaving their wastes. The management should put up at least one trash bin in every cottage. However, it is best to place three trash bins that represent biodegradable, non-biodegradable, and recyclable wastes at every cottage. This is to easily segregate trash and would also be less of a workload for the staff. Having an effective waste segregation system helps to avoid further damage.
2. **Handwash stations.** Handwashing is one of the easiest and efficient way to prevent the spread of viruses and bacteria that can cause sickness and illness. Placing handwashing stations can prevent the contamination and spread of the virus from one person to another. Hand washing stations should have at least two (2) sinks with two bottles of hand soap on the side. An automatic hand air dryer is also necessary.

D. Relation of Waste Management and Hand Washing System in Maintaining a Clean Environment

Waste management system and hand washing stations help to create a clean and safe environment for the tourists. This controls the potential damage that may occur. Waste management system helps to control the waste and separate them into their respective category, while handwashing stations can prevent the spread of viruses and bacteria from one person to another.

II. CONSERVE

With all the actions made in the Protect stage, it will hopefully preserve the beauty of the waterfalls for the future generation to experience it and to prolong the life span of Balite Falls. Limiting the number of tourists who enter Balite Falls per day helps in its conservation. Balite Falls is a small tourist attraction; having a huge crowd may cause pollution. Waste management can also help to improve the quality of air and water. Creating a system, together with maintaining a clean environment, is the key to conserve the tourist attraction of Amadeo. The conservation of Balite Falls is the main goal of this study. However, for it to really take effect, there is a need to raise awareness and educate tourists in conserving the tourist attraction.

A signage is essential for a tourist attraction. A signage gives information and guidelines to tourists. With this, it helps tourists be informed on how to properly use the facilities of Balite Falls and educate them on how everyone has a responsibility and accountability in taking care of such tourist attractions. A signage that gives information should be prioritized. The design of the signage should be readable for all ages; it should also be short and concise. The standard size for a signage is 24 x 36 inches, so that everyone can read the signage properly.

Conclusion

The Philippines is well-known for having a wide variety of tourism, from dark tourism to ecotourism. The country is also known for having diverse and majestic natural tourist attractions and destinations. Beaches, mountains, volcanoes, rivers, caves, reefs, and falls are the Philippines' pride. One of them is a waterfall located in a small municipality in Cavite, Amadeo – Balite Falls.

Balite Falls is a very promising natural tourist attraction in Amadeo, Cavite. People from neighboring cities who wish to take a quick vacation far from the hustle of the cities often go to Balite Falls. Balite Falls is a very convenient destination because it is only two (2) hours away from Manila and is near Tagaytay. Its beauty attracts hundreds of tourists. Balite falls has two small waterfalls. The water is clean, and it is surrounded by green, making its air clean as well. This is a truly must-visit destination, not only due to its undeniable beauty, but also its peacefulness. Balite Falls is also perfect for team building activities and chilling out with family and friends.

The falls has gained attention with the public. Tourists gave good reviews on television shows, travel blogs and reviews, and social media platforms. However, as the population of tourists increase, there is a need to protect and conserve the falls for future generations. The researchers proposed an input of an ecotourism plan for Balite Falls that will help to conserve and enhance its beauty as a natural attraction. According to Rhama (2018), ecotourism policies must be formulated to educate and provide understanding while inviting tourists. The conservation of natural resources is a top priority; it is our duty to protect and conserve these natural resources.

The study observes that the input of an ecotourism plan for Balite falls is a big help in preserving and enhancing its beauty. Through this, it saves its beauty and attracts more potential tourists. Maintaining its natural beauty must be a top priority. The input of the ecotourism plan for Balite Falls mainly focuses on three focal points or strategies. First focal point is to expand the market of the falls through social media, transportation, and tourist products. Second focal point is to maintain and conserve the beauty of Balite falls. Lastly, to improve the satisfaction and experience of tourists.

This study concludes that Balite falls has a great potential to increase the economy of Amadeo and even become a source of living for locals. The government of Amadeo can use this attraction as an instrument to advertise the growing municipality. This also concludes that even if the tourist destination is already beautiful, it still has room for improvement, as it adapts to the fast-changing world.

This study serves as a guide for the next generation and tourism plan makers; it will also help students who are willing to learn more about ecotourism in the Philippines, and tourism in general. This research is designed to be an eye opener for tourism people – government and schools, and even people who are interested in the tourism industry in order for them to make decisions that will help protect natural and man-made tourist attractions and destinations in the country.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations made by the researchers:

1. Create souvenirs and goods that are inspired by Balite Falls. The local government may collaborate with local and small enterprises in making souvenirs for Balite Falls. Products can vary from household equipment or personal items like t-shirts, mugs, canvas bags, keychains, and bracelets. This idea requires the locals are engaged, which may support their day-to-day living skills that may be enhanced.
2. Ensure the cleanliness of the Balite Falls. The management should not allow plastic cups, utensils, and paper plates to minimize waste. Future researchers may modify the study to help with other researches in the same field.
3. Tourism plan makers may use this research as a guide for making ecotourism development plans of different tourist attractions in the Philippines.

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